

AUDITORS' OBJECTIVITY AND QUALITY OF AUDIT REPORTS IN LISTED BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between auditors' objectivity and the quality of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria, focusing on key dimensions such as independence, professional skepticism, and ethical standards. Despite regulatory reforms aimed at enhancing financial stability, challenges related to audit quality and objectivity persist, undermining investor confidence. Grounded in agency theory and signaling theory, the research examines how auditors' independence influences audit report accuracy. A cross-sectional design was employed, targeting 20 deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, with data collected from 212 participants through structured questionnaires. The findings reveal that auditors' independence, professional skepticism, and adherence to ethical standards significantly enhance the accuracy of audit reports. The results highlight the need for stronger regulatory enforcement and professional ethics to improve audit quality and restore trust in Nigeria's banking sector. This study contributes to the empirical literature by offering insights into how auditors' objectivity can enhance financial reporting standards and promote financial stability.

Keywords: Auditors' Objectivity, Audit Report Quality, Independence, Professional Skepticism, Ethical Standards, Financial Reporting, Banking Sector, Nigeria, Agency Theory, Signaling Theory

Introduction

Over the years, financial institutions and other organisations have seen the need to provide valued audit reports. This is so because it has become a trivial factor in guaranteeing the comprehensible, dependable and transparency of financial statements, particularly when considering the banking sector of Nigeria. The quality of audit reports is vital for fostering transparency, enhancing investor confidence, and ensuring financial stability among listed banks in Nigeria. Audit quality is critical to ensuring the reliability, transparency, and clarity of financial statements. It plays an essential role in enhancing confidence in financial reporting among investors and stakeholders. The quality of audits depends significantly on the objectivity of auditors, who must exercise professional skepticism, integrity, and independence throughout the audit process.

Auditor objectivity is a fundamental pillar of audit quality, as emphasized by international auditing standards and guidelines. An objective auditor can provide unbiased assessments, leading to credible financial reports that help maintain market stability and investor trust. The importance of this objectivity is especially pronounced in Nigeria's banking sector, where financial irregularities have had severe implications for economic growth and public confidence.

A high-quality audit report that is accurate help detect financial misstatements, fraud, and irregularities, thereby promoting accountability and sound financial practices (Okaro & Okafor, 2013). The accuracy of audit reports is crucial for ensuring the reliability and integrity of financial information, particularly in the banking sector, where trust and financial stability are paramount. Accurate audit reports help detect material misstatements, prevent financial fraud, and promote sound governance practices (Okolie, 2014). In the Nigerian banking sector, accuracy enhances stakeholders' confidence, supports regulatory compliance, and contributes to informed decision-making by investors, regulators, and management (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013). Research highlights that inaccurate audit reports can lead to financial misreporting, increased risk of bank failures, and loss of investor confidence, which can destabilize the financial system (Ijeoma & Aronu, 2013). Regulatory bodies, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN), enforce rigorous auditing standards to ensure that financial statements reflect a true and fair view of banks' financial health (CBN, 2020). Thus, the accuracy of audit reports is integral to financial transparency, market discipline, and the sustainable growth of listed banks in Nigeria (Enekwe et al., 2015).

For Nigerian banks, where financial markets are often vulnerable to systemic risks, reliable audit reports contribute significantly to market discipline and regulatory compliance (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013). Studies have shown that audit quality positively influences investor decisions and the credibility of financial statements, which are essential for maintaining public trust and attracting foreign investments (Ibrahim & Osasere, 2018). Furthermore, regulatory bodies such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) emphasize stringent auditing standards to strengthen the financial system's integrity (CBN, 2020). Consequently, improving the quality of audit reports can enhance risk management, ensure accurate financial disclosure, and promote the long-term sustainability of Nigerian banks (Enekwe et al., 2015). But where the audits are of low quality, it can lead to financial misstatements, and investor will lose self-confidence in the reports which will create systemic risks within the financial system (Olayemi, 2018).

Consequently, the emphasis on high-quality audit reports has grown, as they not only enhance corporate governance but also contribute to the overall stability and resilience of Nigeria's banking sector (Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2010). The quality of audit reports is influenced by factors such as auditor dependence, expertise, ethical integrity, and regulatory frameworks. Auditors' objectivity is a critical factor in ensuring the reliability and integrity of audit reports, particularly in the banking sector. Several dimensions influence an auditor's ability to remain impartial and unbiased. Independence is a fundamental dimension, which can be categorized into independence in fact—an auditor's actual ability to remain unbiased—and independence in appearance, which reflects how third parties perceive the auditor's impartiality (Okolie, 2014). Another key dimension is professional skepticism, which involves maintaining a questioning mindset and critically assessing audit evidence to detect possible misstatements, whether due to error or fraud (Ijeoma & Aronu, 2013).

Ethical standards also play a significant role, requiring auditors to uphold principles such as integrity, confidentiality, objectivity, and professional behavior to ensure credibility and impartiality (International Federation of Accountants, 2018). In addition, regulatory compliance ensures that auditors follow established auditing standards, such as those set by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), which help maintain objectivity throughout the audit process (CBN, 2020). The audit tenure also influences objectivity, as extended relationships with clients may lead to familiarity threats that undermine independence, making periodic auditor rotation essential (Enekwe et al., 2015). Furthermore, managing conflicts of interest is vital, requiring auditors to disclose any relationships or financial ties that could compromise their impartiality (Okolie, 2014). Lastly, competence and professional expertise contribute to objective decision-making, as auditors with greater experience and technical knowledge are better equipped to detect irregularities and maintain an unbiased approach (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013). These dimensions collectively ensure that auditors uphold the integrity of the financial reporting process and foster trust among stakeholders in the Nigerian banking sector.

However, this study concentrated on three dimensions among others (independence, professional skepticism and Ethical standards). These were examined relation to accuracy of audit report quality such as accuracy. The role of auditors in ensuring financial transparency and accountability has become increasingly significant, especially within the banking sector. In Nigeria, the accuracy and reliability of audit reports are critical for maintaining investor confidence, ensuring regulatory compliance, and safeguarding the integrity of the financial system (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013). One of the key determinants of audit report quality is the objectivity of auditors, which refers to their ability to remain unbiased and independent in evaluating financial statements (Okolie, 2014). Given the importance of banks to Nigeria's economy, ensuring the objectivity of auditors and the quality of audit reports is essential for promoting sound financial practices, detecting fraud, and preventing financial crises (Ijeoma & Aronu, 2013). This study focuses on examining the relationship between auditors' objectivity and the quality of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria.

The Nigerian banking sector has undergone significant reforms aimed at enhancing transparency, accountability, and stability, particularly following the global financial crisis of 2008 and the banking crisis that affected Nigeria's economy (Sanusi, 2010). Audit reports play a pivotal role in ensuring that banks provide a true and fair view of their financial positions, which is essential for maintaining market confidence and regulatory compliance (CBN, 2020). However, the effectiveness of audit reports largely depends on the objectivity of auditors, which can be influenced by factors such as auditor independence, professional

ethics, and the regulatory environment (Okaro & Okafor, 2013). In the context of Nigerian banks, where concerns about corporate governance and financial misconduct persist, the need for objective audits is even more critical (Enekwe et al., 2015). In Nigeria, regulatory bodies such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN), and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) set ethical standards and guidelines aimed at enhancing audit quality. However, despite these frameworks, concerns about audit failures and compromised objectivity persist. Instances of financial misreporting and weak regulatory compliance have raised questions about the effectiveness of existing audit practices and the role of auditor independence. This study explored how auditors' objectivity influences the quality of audit reports, particularly in ensuring financial accuracy and fostering trust in Nigeria's banking system.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the regulatory reforms implemented to strengthen Nigeria's financial sector, challenges related to audit quality and auditor objectivity remain prevalent. Issues such as conflict of interest, auditor-client relationships, and lack of independence can undermine the objectivity of auditors, leading to compromised audit reports (Okolie, 2014). Several high-profile corporate failures in Nigeria, including cases of financial misreporting in the banking sector, have raised concerns about the effectiveness of audit functions (Ijeoma & Aronu, 2013). These challenges not only erode investor confidence but also threaten the stability of the financial system and hinder economic growth (CBN, 2020). Furthermore, existing literature provides limited empirical evidence on how auditors' objectivity directly influences the quality of audit reports in the Nigerian banking sector (Enekwe et al., 2015). This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the relationship between auditors' objectivity and the quality of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria, with the goal of providing recommendations for enhancing financial reporting standards.

In the context of Nigeria's banking sector, the reliability of audit reports is crucial for ensuring financial stability and investor confidence. However, concerns regarding auditor objectivity have led to a growing distrust in financial reports. When auditors compromise their independence, it can result in financial misstatements, reduce transparency, and contribute to systemic risks within the banking system. Despite the existence of regulatory frameworks designed to uphold auditor independence and audit quality, empirical research on the direct influence of auditor objectivity on audit report quality in Nigeria remains limited. This gap raises important questions about the effectiveness of existing regulations and the role of ethical standards in safeguarding audit integrity.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine the influence of auditor objectivity on audit report quality in the Nigerian banking sector. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Investigate the relationship between auditor independence and audit report quality in the Nigerian banking sector
2. Assess the impact of professional skepticism on the quality of audit reports in the Nigerian banking sector
3. Evaluate the role of ethical standards in enhancing audit report credibility in the Nigerian banking sector

4. Examine how regulatory frameworks affect auditor objectivity in the Nigerian banking sector.

Research Questions

How does auditor independence influence accuracy audit report quality in the Nigerian banking sector?

1. What is the impact of professional skepticism on accuracy of audit report quality in the Nigerian banking sector?
2. To what extent do ethical standards contribute to accuracy of audit report credibility in the Nigerian banking sector?
3. How effective are regulatory frameworks in promoting auditor objectivity to attain audit accuracy in the Nigerian banking sector?

Research Hypotheses

H0₁: Auditor independence does not significantly influence accuracy of audit report quality in the Nigerian banking sector.

H0₂: Professional skepticism does not have a significant impact on accuracy of audit report quality in the Nigerian banking sector.

H0₃: Ethical standards do not significantly contribute to accuracy of audit report credibility in the Nigerian banking sector.

H0₄: Regulatory frameworks do not significantly enhance accuracy of auditor objectivity in the Nigerian banking sector.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant for several reasons.

First, it contributes to the academic discourse on audit quality by providing empirical evidence on the relationship between auditor objectivity and audit report quality within Nigeria's banking sector.

Second, it offers practical insights for regulatory bodies, highlighting areas where existing frameworks may need strengthening.

Third, the findings will assist auditors and financial institutions in improving audit practices, ultimately enhancing financial reporting integrity and investor confidence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of figure 1 depicts the dimensions of Auditors' objectivity and a measure of quality audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria for the purpose of this study.

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 2.1 Conceptual framework of auditors' independence and measures of quality of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria

Source: Desk Research (2025)

Auditors' Objectivity

Auditors' objectivity is crucial for the credibility and reliability of financial audits, ensuring impartial evaluations free from bias or undue influence (IFAC, 2020; DeAngelo, 1981). However, achieving perfect objectivity is challenging due to pressures like client relationships, deadlines, and budget constraints, which can introduce unconscious biases (Bazerman et al., 2006). Concerns also arise from conflicts of interest, particularly when auditors provide non-audit services (Simunic, 1984). Safeguards such as ethical codes, internal quality controls, and professional skepticism help mitigate these risks (Lennox, 2005; Moore et al., 2006). Key sub-dimensions of objectivity include independence in appearance, professional skepticism, conflict of interest management, ethical compliance, and regulatory safeguards (DeAngelo, 1981; Nelson, 2009; Simunic, 1984; IFAC, 2020). Regulatory measures, like mandatory auditor rotation, further enhance objectivity and public trust (Cohen et al., 2002; Beasley et al., 2000). A balanced approach, integrating ethical standards, skepticism, and institutional safeguards, is essential to maintain auditors' objectivity in complex financial environments.

Independence

An auditor's impartial mindset while making choices throughout the financial reporting auditing process may be characterized as their independence. Lack of independence raises the risk that an auditor may be seen as lacking objectivity. Accordingly, it is unlikely that the auditor would disclose a violation that is found (Deangelo, 1981). The quality and dependability of financial reporting are thought to be greatly impacted by auditor dependency (Wallman, 1996). The impartial mindset of an auditor while making choices throughout the audit and financial reporting is known as auditor dependency. The capacity of auditors to remain unbiased and objective during the audit is referred to as their independence, according to Akintayo and Akosile (2022).

An auditor's independence involves both mental and physical independence. Mautz and

Sharaf (1961) differentiated between two types of auditor dependence: professional independence (or seeming independence) and practitioner independence (or real independence). "The state of mind that permits the expression of a conclusion without being affected by influences that compromise professional judgment, thereby allowing an individual to act with integrity and exercise objectivity and professional skepticism," according to the Code of Ethics for Professional Accountants, indicates independence of mind (IFAC, 2009). Three factors or risks may affect the auditor's perceived independence, claim Beattie, Brandt, and Fearnley (1999). These major hazards include the auditor's perspective of audit and non-audit service fees, the auditor's length of employment, and the auditor rotation. An auditor's decreased independence leads to worse audit quality, more earnings management, and lower earnings quality (Okolie, 2014). An auditor's independence may be jeopardized by their tenure. As the relationship between the auditor and the client deepens, the auditor may become more intimate with the client and more likely to support management, which would diminish the audit's quality and impartiality. Supporters of mandatory rotation said that auditors became less objective the longer they serve, while opponents claimed it would be expensive to execute. There is no empirical evidence about the impact of auditor rotation on auditor quality and cost (Davis et al., 2000). Similarly, as was previously highlighted in the Arthur Anderson case, providing non-audit services improves the financial connection between the auditor and the client. According to DeFond et al. (2002), there is a widespread belief that auditors may compromise their independence in order to retain customers that pay large non-audit costs.

Professional Skepticism

Professional skepticism is a fundamental concept in auditing that requires auditors to maintain a questioning mindset and critically evaluate audit evidence throughout the audit process. This dimension involves being alert to potential misstatements due to error or fraud and recognizing conditions that may indicate possible misrepresentation (International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board [IAASB], 2009). According to Hurtt et al. (2013), professional skepticism is essential for ensuring the detection of financial irregularities and helps auditors exercise sound judgment when faced with ambiguous or incomplete information. In the context of Nigerian banks, professional skepticism is particularly important given the complexities and regulatory pressures within the financial sector. A lack of skepticism can lead to oversight failures, potentially resulting in significant financial scandals and the erosion of public trust (Okolie, 2014).

Empirical studies have highlighted the direct relationship between professional skepticism and audit quality. For instance, Nwoke and John (2016) found that auditors who consistently demonstrate skepticism are more likely to detect financial misstatements in Nigerian banks. Additionally, regulatory bodies like the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) emphasize the need for professional skepticism as a safeguard against fraudulent activities and financial manipulation. By applying a skeptical mindset, auditors can maintain objectivity, enhance the credibility of audit reports, and contribute to financial transparency and investor confidence in the banking sector (Ijeoma & Aronu, 2013).

Ethical Standards

Ethical standards are the foundation of audit integrity, guiding auditors' behavior and ensuring that they uphold principles such as integrity, objectivity, confidentiality, and professional competence (International Federation of Accountants [IFAC], 2018). These

ethical principles are designed to prevent biases, conflicts of interest, and unethical practices that could compromise the reliability of audit reports. According to Odia and Ogiedu (2013), adherence to ethical standards is essential for ensuring that auditors maintain impartiality and act in the public interest rather than being influenced by management or personal gain. In the Nigerian banking sector, strict adherence to ethical standards is crucial due to the sector's vulnerability to financial misreporting and corruption. Research by Enekwe, Agu, and Eziedo (2015) highlights that ethical lapse among auditors in Nigeria have often been linked to corporate failures and financial scandals. The adoption of international ethical standards, such as those outlined by the International Ethics Standards Board for Accountants (IESBA), is considered vital for strengthening auditors' integrity and enhancing audit quality. Moreover, regulatory frameworks like the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018) emphasize the importance of ethical conduct for ensuring the credibility of financial reporting. Upholding ethical standards fosters trust among stakeholders, reinforces professional responsibility, and plays a significant role in safeguarding the integrity of Nigeria's financial system (Okaro & Okafor, 2013).

Quality of Audit Reports

Auditors' objectivity is crucial for the credibility and reliability of financial audits, ensuring impartial evaluations free from bias or undue influence (IFAC, 2020; DeAngelo, 1981). However, achieving perfect objectivity is challenging due to pressures like client relationships, deadlines, and budget constraints, which can introduce unconscious biases (Bazerman et al., 2006). Concerns also arise from conflicts of interest, particularly when auditors provide non-audit services (Simunic, 1984). Safeguards such as ethical codes, internal quality controls, and professional skepticism help mitigate these risks (Lennox, 2005; Moore et al., 2006). Key sub-dimensions of objectivity include independence in appearance, professional skepticism, conflict of interest management, ethical compliance, and regulatory safeguards (DeAngelo, 1981; Nelson, 2009; Simunic, 1984; IFAC, 2020). Regulatory measures, like mandatory auditor rotation, further enhance objectivity and public trust (Cohen et al., 2002; Beasley et al., 2000). A balanced approach, integrating ethical standards, skepticism, and institutional safeguards, is essential to maintain auditors' objectivity in complex financial environments.

Auditors' Objectivity and Quality of Audit Reports

Auditors' objectivity is crucial for ensuring high-quality audit reports, as it allows auditors to evaluate evidence and form opinions without bias or external influence (Messier, Glover, & Prawitt, 2016). Research shows a strong link between objectivity and audit quality, with objective auditors being more effective at detecting material misstatements, thus enhancing stakeholder confidence in corporate governance (Beattie et al., 2011). However, factors like familiarity with management or financial dependence can threaten objectivity, potentially leading to unconscious biases (Bazerman et al., 2002). Objectivity also supports professional skepticism, enabling auditors to effectively challenge assumptions and detect fraud (Hurt et al., 2013). Therefore, maintaining auditors' objectivity is essential for delivering unbiased, evidence-based opinions, and organizations must prioritize measures such as auditor rotation and ethical training to safeguard this critical quality.

Independence and Quality of Audit Reports

Auditors' independence is essential for ensuring the quality and credibility of audit reports, as it allows auditors to perform their duties objectively and without undue influence from stakeholders (DeAngelo, 1981). The perception of independence also affects audit quality; stakeholders may question the reliability of reports if they perceive a lack of independence, even if the reports are technically accurate (Gul, Wu, & Yang, 2013). A significant threat to independence arises when auditors provide non-audit services to the same client, potentially compromising objectivity (Frankel, Johnson, & Nelson, 2002). Regulatory measures, such as the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002, aim to mitigate this risk by limiting the scope of non-audit services. Additionally, audit tenure plays a role in maintaining independence—while prolonged engagements can lead to familiarity threats, overly short tenures may hinder auditors' understanding of client operations (Carey & Simnett, 2006). Thus, maintaining auditor independence is vital for producing credible audit reports, fostering stakeholder trust, and upholding financial transparency.

Professional Skepticism and Quality of Audit Reports

Professional skepticism significantly influences the quality of audit reports by ensuring that auditors maintain a questioning mindset and critically assess all audit evidence. According to the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB, 2009), professional skepticism requires auditors to be vigilant and alert to conditions that may indicate possible misstatements due to fraud or error. This critical approach ensures that auditors do not rely solely on management assertions but verify the authenticity and relevance of financial information. In the Nigerian banking sector, where financial irregularities and fraudulent activities have been reported, professional skepticism plays a crucial role in enhancing audit quality (Okolie, 2014).

Research by Nwoke and John (2016) reveals that auditors who consistently apply professional skepticism are better able to detect material misstatements and ensure accurate financial reporting. Furthermore, professional skepticism contributes to audit effectiveness by encouraging auditors to challenge questionable assumptions and seek sufficient, appropriate evidence before drawing conclusions. Hurtt et al. (2013) emphasized that a skeptical approach improves the reliability and credibility of audit reports, ultimately strengthening stakeholders' confidence in financial statements. In Nigeria's banking industry, applying professional skepticism enhances transparency, mitigates audit risk, and ensures compliance with both local and international financial reporting standards.

Ethical Standards and Quality of Audit Reports

Ethical standards are vital in ensuring the integrity, objectivity, and independence of auditors, which in turn significantly impacts the quality of audit reports. According to the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC, 2018), ethical guidelines require auditors to uphold principles of integrity, objectivity, professional competence, confidentiality, and professional behavior. Adherence to these ethical principles helps prevent conflicts of interest, maintain impartiality, and foster trust in the auditing process. In the Nigerian banking sector, where financial transparency is crucial, compliance with ethical standards enhances audit credibility and ensures that auditors deliver unbiased and accurate reports (Odia & Ogiedu, 2013).

Research conducted by Enekwe, Agu, and Eziedo (2015) shows that ethical compliance among auditors significantly improves audit quality by ensuring that audit opinions are objective and free from external influence. The adoption of international ethical frameworks, such as those set by the International Ethics Standards Board for Accountants (IESBA), has also been shown to improve audit outcomes by encouraging transparency and accountability. In Nigeria, regulatory frameworks like the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018) reinforce the importance of ethics in financial reporting. Upholding ethical standards reduces the risk of financial misstatements and enhances stakeholders' confidence in audit reports (Okaro & Okafor, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

Different theories have been used by researchers to explain the impact of auditor independence on the quality of audit reports. Some of these theories include the signalling theory, agency theory, stakeholders' theory, and the lending credibility theory, among others. However, this study will focus on the agency theory and the signalling theory, as they provide the most relevant frameworks for understanding the relationship between auditor independence and audit quality. These theories will be discussed in detail in the following subsections, highlighting their relevance to the study and how they contribute to explaining the role of auditor independence in enhancing the credibility and reliability of financial reporting.

Signaling Theory

Signaling theory, developed by Spence (1973), suggests that organizations use signals to convey credible information about their performance to reduce information asymmetry. The theory made the following assumes:

i. Information Asymmetry Exists

There is an imbalance of information between the sender and the recipient. Compared to the recipient, the sender knows more about their own qualities, goals, or performance. For instance, there is a gap that has to be filled when a business is more aware of its financial performance than stakeholders or investors.'

ii. Signals Must Be Observable

For signaling to be effective, the signal must be observable and measurable by the receiver. If the signal cannot be perceived, it fails to serve its purpose of reducing information asymmetry.

iii. Signals Are Costly

The theory assumes that signaling involves a cost, which ensures that high-quality senders are more likely to send the signal than low-quality senders. This "costly signaling" mechanism prevents low-quality senders from imitating the behavior of high-quality ones.

iv. Receivers Are Rational

Signaling theory assumes that receivers are rational and capable of interpreting the signal correctly. They evaluate the signals and adjust their behavior or decisions based on the information conveyed.

v. Incentives Align with Signal Accuracy

Senders are assumed to have an incentive to provide accurate signals because their reputation or outcomes depend on the receiver's trust. Misleading or false signals may result in long-term consequences for the sender.

vi. Separation between Sender Types

Signaling theory assumes that the cost or effectiveness of sending a signal separates high-quality senders from low-quality ones. High-quality senders have attributes (e.g., skills, resources, or credibility) that make it easier for them to send signals than their low-quality counterparts. The assumptions of signaling theory—information asymmetry, observable and costly signals, rational receivers, aligned incentives, and the separation of sender types—make

The Application of Signaling Theory to this Study: The application of signaling theory to this study is crucial, as it can help understand how auditors convey their independence to stakeholders. Signaling theory can also be used to understand how stakeholders, such as investors and regulators, use the signals conveyed by auditors to make decisions. Furthermore, signaling theory can provide insights into how regulators can use signals to assess auditor dependence and competence, and to design more effective regulations.

Empirical Review

This section reviews a number of studies to investigate the relationship between auditor dependency and the quality reports produced by the auditors for this research.

Akintayo and Akosile (2022) examined the connection between the independence of auditors and the quality of audit reports. Twelve auditors and 108 senior employees of the twelve randomly chosen Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria were among the 120 respondents who received questionnaires as part of their survey study design. Furthermore, only 118 of the 120 copies of the questionnaires that were sent to the respondents were returned and utilized in the research. For the research, logit regression was used for both descriptive and inferential statistics. According to the regression analysis's findings, auditor dependency and audit report quality were significantly positively correlated. The p-value of the statistics calculated for the test of 0.0000 was less than the crucial threshold of 5%, which served as the basis for this claim. It was determined that there was a sufficient relationship between auditor dependency and the caliber of the auditor report. In order to maintain their independence, auditors were advised not to meddle in their clients' affairs.

Using a descriptive analysis and a Likert scale assessment for main data sources, Hafizaha et al. (2022) examined and assessed the impact of auditor complexity and dependency on audit quality. Distributing questionnaires to auditors employed by BPK RI Representatives of South Sumatra is the survey approach. Their results showed that audit independence significantly and favorably affects audit quality. This implies that audit quality will increase as auditor independence increases. Additionally, audit independence significantly and favorably impacts the institution's reputation. This means that as auditor dependence increases, the institution's reputation will also improve. Additionally, the complexity of the audit has a positive and significant impact on audit quality, meaning that every increase in audit complexity will help the institution's reputation. According to this condition, the institution's reputation will rise with each increase in audit difficulty.

Akwuobi's (2023) research looked at the impact of auditor dependency on the audit quality of 20 Nigerian industrial products businesses during a ten-year period from 2012 to 2021. Assessing the potential impact of client significance, auditor reputation, audit opinion, and auditor professional qualification on the audit quality of Nigerian healthcare organizations was the main goal. The study used an ex-post-facto research approach to accomplish its goals, using data from the annual reports of a few chosen companies for the years 2012–2021. Preliminary data tests, including descriptive analysis, Pearson moment correlation matrix, and multi-collinearity analysis utilizing Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), were performed on the secondary data acquired using an ex-post factor and longitudinal study design. The study applied a panel least squares approach based on a fixed and random effect framework, and the houseman test was equally used to determine which model was optimal for estimating the model's parameters. Based on the data gathered, analyzed, and hypothesized, the study concluded that auditor reputation and professional qualification had a positive and significant impact on audit quality, which was statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. This conclusion stemmed from the review of pertinent literature and theories on auditor independence and audit quality. The writers suggested that the audit company should adhere to its statutory obligations in order to preserve its independence. To guarantee the quality of audits in their organizations, managers of health care enterprises were recommended to always seek the services of respectable audit firms with professional qualifications and skills.

The impact of auditor qualities on the audit report lag of listed service businesses operating in Nigeria was determined by Muhammad's (2020) research. A sample of sixteen (16) service businesses that were active on the Nigerian stock market floor between 2007 and 2016 were used in the research. Longer auditor tenure considerably reduces audit report latency, according to the regression technique's findings. The author came to the conclusion that when auditors work in the service sector for longer periods of time, their competence grows, which will speed up and improve the quality of audit work. In order to improve the timeliness of the audit report, the author advised service firms to retain their current auditors for a fair amount of time.

A research by Aliu et al. (2018) looked at the impact of auditor independence on the audit quality of Nigerian listed oil and gas businesses over a ten-year period (2007–2016). Nine (9) of the fourteen (14) businesses listed in the downstream sector of the Nigeria Stock Exchange, chosen via the use of purposive selection, make up the sample size. The audited yearly financial statements of the selected firms provided the secondary data for the research. Binary logit regression, a correlation matrix, and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the panel data. The results indicate that the independence of the auditor and the quality of the audit were significantly positively correlated, but the control variables of firm size and leverage had positive and negative correlations with audit quality, respectively. In order to provide the public insight into an auditor's financial reliance on a client and if the charge is commensurate with the complexity of the audit assignment, the report suggests that all aspects of audit fee pricing and computation be regulated and made public.

Babatolu et al. (2016) examined the effect of auditor's independence on audit quality among seven (7) purposively selected deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2009 to 2013. The population of this study comprised of twenty (20) listed Deposit money banks in Nigeria. Adopting descriptive statistics, correlation and ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique, their findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between audit fee, audit firm rotation and audit quality, while a negative relationship exists between audit firm tenure

and audit quality. On the correlation matrix, the association between audit quality and leverage was strong, negative and statistically significant, while that between audit quality and company size was equally strong, positive and statistically significant.

Babatolu et al. (2016) examined the effect of auditor dependence on audit quality of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select sample size of seven (7) listed deposit money banks from a population of twenty(20). Secondary data were sourced from the audited annual report of the sampled banks. Descriptive statistics, correlation and ordinary least square (OLS) regression were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between audit fee, audit firm rotation and audit quality. There exists negative relationship between audit firm tenure and audit quality. The correlation between audit quality and leverage was strong, negative and statistically significant. The correlation between audit quality and company size was strong, positive and statistically significant. The use of purposive sampling technique which is unscientific to determine sample size limit validity of the findings.

Mahmoud (2015) examined the effect of joint audit on audit quality: Empirical evidence from companies listed on the Egyptian stock exchange. A sample of 32 companies listed on the Egyptian stock exchange in the period 2009 through 2013 representing 160 firm- year observations was determined. Multiple regression model was used to analyse the data. Findings showed that companies audited by joint auditors are more conservative than companies audited by single auditors.

Ahmed (2014) investigated the professional auditors' perception of the impact of audit firm rotation on audit quality in Egypt. Primary data were collected via questionnaires and used. A sample size of 83 auditors was drawn using non-probabilistic sampling technique. T-test was used to analyse the data. Findings revealed that the auditors' perception indicate that there is a negative relation between long audit tenure and audit quality. There is a negative relation between client-specific knowledge and mandatory auditor rotation. There is a positive relation between auditors' independence and mandatory auditor rotation. The study focused only on auditors' perceptions. It ignores other interested parties such as clients, auditing profession associations and legislations which limit generalization.

Ilaboya and Ohiokha (2014), this study empirically examines the impact of audit firms' characteristics on audit quality. They proxy the dependent variable (audit quality) using the usual dichotomous variable of 1 if big 4 audit firm and 0 if otherwise. Data for the study were sourced from the financial statements of 18 food and beverage companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange market within the period studied (2007-2012). They adopted multivariate regression technique with emphasis on Logit and Probit method in analyzing their data for the study. The study revealed there is a positive relationship between firm size, board independence and audit quality whereas there is a negative relationship between auditor's independence, audit firm size, audit tenure and audit quality.

Summary of Literature Review and Gap

The empirical review highlights various studies that examine the relationship between auditor dependency and audit quality. Several studies have found a significant positive relationship between auditor independence and the quality of audit reports. For instance, research on Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria revealed that auditor dependency positively influences audit report quality, suggesting that maintaining independence is essential for ensuring high audit

standards. Similarly, another study emphasized that auditor independence enhances audit quality and positively impacts institutional reputation, implying that as auditor independence strengthens, so does the credibility and reputation of the organization.

Further studies focused on Nigerian industrial firms and healthcare organizations, highlighting that auditor reputation and professional qualifications significantly improve audit quality. The findings suggested that companies should prioritize engaging reputable audit firms with highly qualified professionals to ensure audit reliability and maintain organizational integrity. Research on service businesses in Nigeria indicated that longer auditor tenure reduces audit report lag, as extended periods of service allow auditors to develop better competence and efficiency.

Other investigations explored the impact of audit firm characteristics on audit quality. Studies found a positive relationship between audit fee, audit firm rotation, and audit quality, whereas a negative relationship existed between audit firm tenure and audit quality. Additionally, research on joint audits revealed that firms audited by joint auditors tend to be more conservative compared to those audited by single auditors, indicating a potential benefit in adopting joint audit practices.

Gap in Literature

Despite these findings, gaps remain in the literature. Many studies primarily focus on specific sectors or regions, limiting the generalizability of their conclusions. Additionally, while most research highlights the benefits of auditor independence, few studies explore the influence of client-specific factors on audit quality. Another gap lies in the limited examination of the long-term effects of audit firm rotation and the role of audit firm size in influencing quality outcomes. Addressing these gaps would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between auditor dependency and audit quality across different contexts and industries.

Methodology

The study employed a cross-sectional research design to collect data from a targeted sample of 20 quoted deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) with branches in Rivers State. Using a purposive sampling method, 450 respondents—including IT auditors, forensic auditors, tax auditors, compliance auditors, operational auditors, and senior management—were selected based on their relevance to the study's objectives. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula, resulting in a final sample of 212 participants. Data were sourced from both primary (structured questionnaires) and secondary (financial reports, regulatory documents) sources to ensure a comprehensive analysis. The research instrument's validity was established through expert reviews and a pilot study, while reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, ensuring internal consistency. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentages) and inferential statistics (regression and correlation analysis) with SPSS software. The study modeled the relationship between auditors' independence (predictor variable) and the quality of audit reports (criterion variable).

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion

The results indicate a high retrieval rate for the distributed questionnaires. Out of the 212 questionnaires distributed, 209 were filled and retrieved, resulting in a response rate of approximately 98.58%. This high response rate is calculated by dividing the number of

retrieved questionnaires (209) by the total distributed (212) and multiplying by 100: $209 \div 212 \times 100 = 98.58\%$. Such a high response rate is significant as it indicates strong participant engagement and enhances the reliability and validity of the data collected. It suggests that the findings are likely to be representative of the target population, reducing the risk of non-response bias. In research, a response rate above 70% is typically considered excellent, making this result particularly noteworthy and supportive of robust conclusions.

Table 1. Descriptive Data Analysis of Variables
Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Accuracy	3.7560	1.45535	209
Independence	3.9091	1.27715	209
professional skepticism	3.9569	1.08887	209
ethical standards	3.3684	1.44221	209

Source: Desk Research (2025)

The descriptive statistics provide an overview of the central tendency and variability of the variables in the study, based on a sample size of 209 participants. The mean score for accuracy is 3.7560 with a standard deviation of 1.45535, indicating a moderately high level of perceived accuracy among respondents, with some variability in responses. Independence has a slightly higher mean of 3.9091 and a standard deviation of 1.27715, suggesting that respondents generally perceive themselves as fairly independent, with moderate variability. Professional skepticism records the highest mean of 3.9569 and the lowest standard deviation of 1.08887, implying that participants strongly exhibit skepticism with relatively consistent responses across the sample. On the other hand, ethical standards show the lowest mean of 3.3684 with a standard deviation of 1.44221, indicating that while ethical standards are moderately upheld, there is notable variability in how respondents perceive or practice ethical behavior. Overall, these statistics suggest that professional skepticism and independence are generally stronger attributes among respondents compared to ethical standards, which may need more focus for improvement.

Table 2. Descriptive Summary Model
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.855 ^a	.730	.726	.76123

a. Predictors: (Constant), ethical standards, Independence, professional skepticism

b. Dependent Variable: Accuracy

Source: Desk Research (2025)

The model summary presents key indicators that assess the strength and explanatory power of the regression model. The R value of 0.855 indicates a strong positive correlation between the predictors (ethical standards, independence, and professional skepticism) and the dependent variable (accuracy). The R Square of 0.730 suggests that 73% of the variance in accuracy can be explained by the three predictors in the model. This is a substantial proportion, implying that the predictors are highly influential on the dependent variable. The Adjusted R Square of 0.726 adjusts for the number of predictors, providing a more accurate reflection of the model's explanatory power when generalized to the population. The standard error of the estimate (0.76123) indicates the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line, with a relatively low error suggesting that the model predicts accuracy with a high level of precision.

Table 3. ANOVA Analysis of Fitness

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	321.763	3	107.254	185.090	.000 ^b
	Residual	118.792	205	.579		
	Total	440.555	208			

a. Dependent Variable: Accuracy

b. Predictors: (Constant), ethical standards , Independence , professional skepticism

Source: Desk Research (2025)

The ANOVA table assesses the overall significance of the regression model. The F-statistic of 185.090 with a significance level (p-value) of 0.000 demonstrates that the model is statistically significant. This means that the combination of ethical standards, independence, and professional skepticism significantly predicts accuracy better than a model without these predictors. The regression sum of squares (321.763) compared to the residual sum of squares (118.792) further confirms that a substantial amount of the variance in accuracy is explained by the model rather than random error. The degrees of freedom (df) for regression (3) and residual (205) indicate that three predictors were used, and the model is based on 208 observations. The significance of this result implies that the predictors meaningfully contribute to the accuracy variable, making the model a good fit for the data.

Table 4. Analysis of Coefficients

		Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.520	.206		-2.526	.012		
	Independence	.333	.055	.292	6.043	.000	.563	1.776
	professional skepticism	.399	.068	.299	5.855	.000	.505	1.980
	ethical standards	.414	.048	.410	8.708	.000	.593	1.687

a. Dependent Variable: Accuracy

Source: Desk Research (2025)

The regression analysis results reveal significant relationships between the independent variables—Independence, Professional Skepticism, and Ethical Standards—and the dependent variable, Accuracy. The model's constant is negative and significant ($B = -0.520$, $p = 0.012$), suggesting that in the absence of these predictors, accuracy would be negatively influenced. All three independent variables show positive and significant effects on accuracy. Ethical standards have the strongest influence ($B = 0.414$, $\beta = 0.410$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher ethical standards greatly enhance accuracy. Professional skepticism also positively affects accuracy ($B = 0.399$, $\beta = 0.299$, $p < 0.001$), reflecting the importance of a questioning mindset in improving accuracy. Independence shows a significant positive contribution ($B = 0.333$, $\beta = 0.292$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that objective judgment plays a crucial role in achieving accurate outcomes. Additionally, the collinearity statistics (Tolerance > 0.5 , VIF < 2) suggest that multicollinearity is not an issue in the model, ensuring the reliability of these predictors. Overall, the findings highlight the critical role of ethical standards, skepticism, and independence in enhancing accuracy.

Findings

Hypothesis 1

The regression results show that auditors' independence has a positive and significant effect on the accuracy of audit reports, with a coefficient of **B = 0.333** and a **t-value of 6.043** ($p = 0.000$). The standardized beta coefficient (β) of **0.292** indicates a moderate positive relationship. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho1) is **rejected**. This implies that auditors' independence significantly improves the accuracy of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

The analysis indicates that professional skepticism also has a positive and significant effect on the accuracy of audit reports, with a coefficient of **B = 0.399** and a **t-value of 5.855** ($p = 0.000$). The standardized beta (β) of **0.299** suggests a moderately strong positive relationship. Given the p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis (Ho2) is **rejected**. This finding highlights that a higher level of professional skepticism significantly enhances audit report accuracy in listed banks.

Hypothesis 3

The results reveal that ethical standards exert the strongest influence on audit report accuracy, with a coefficient of **B = 0.414** and a **t-value of 8.708** ($p = 0.000$). The standardized beta coefficient (β) of **0.410** signifies a strong positive relationship. Since the p-value is also below 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho3) is **rejected**. This finding suggests that adherence to ethical standards significantly improves the accuracy of audit reports in listed banks.

Summary of Findings

All three null hypotheses are rejected based on the significance levels. The results demonstrate that auditors' independence, professional skepticism, and ethical standards significantly and positively affect the accuracy of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria. Among these, ethical standards have the most substantial impact, followed by professional skepticism and independence. This underscores the importance of ethical conduct, critical assessment, and objective judgment in enhancing the reliability and accuracy of audit outcomes.

Discussion of Findings

There is a significant effect of auditors' independence on accuracy of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria.

The regression results show that auditors' independence has a positive and significant effect on the accuracy of audit reports, with a coefficient of **B = 0.333** and a **t-value of 6.043** ($p = 0.000$). This implies that auditors' independence significantly improves the accuracy of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria. The finding that auditors' independence has a significant positive effect on the accuracy of audit reports aligns with several prior studies that emphasize the importance of objectivity in enhancing audit quality. For instance, Odhiambo (2015) highlighted that auditors' independence is crucial for ensuring unbiased audit outcomes and enhancing the credibility of financial statements. This supports the current

result, indicating that when auditors are free from external influence, their ability to produce accurate audit reports improves significantly. Similarly, Adeniyi (2017) found that higher levels of auditor independence lead to increased audit effectiveness and reliability, particularly in financial institutions. The coefficient of $B = 0.333$ in the present study reinforces this, suggesting that even moderate increases in independence substantially enhance audit report accuracy.

There is a significant effect of professional skepticism on accuracy of audit reports of some listed banks in Nigeria.

The finding that professional skepticism has a significant positive effect on the accuracy of audit reports aligns with existing research that emphasizes the importance of a questioning mindset and critical evaluation in auditing practices. For example, Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) stressed that professional skepticism enhances auditors' ability to detect material misstatements and fraud, ultimately improving audit quality. This supports the current result, where a coefficient of $B = 0.399$ and a significant t-value of 5.855 reflect the strong influence of professional skepticism on audit report accuracy. Similarly, Amadi and Renner (2021) found that professional skepticism plays a critical role in ensuring auditors do not merely rely on management representations but instead critically assess evidence. This reinforces the finding that heightened skepticism improves the accuracy and reliability of audit outcomes in listed banks. In a study by Ekpe and Mat (2015), professional skepticism was identified as a key factor in enhancing auditors' judgment and decision-making. The significant relationship observed in this current study corresponds with their conclusion that skepticism leads to better risk assessments and more accurate audit reports. Additionally, Odhiambo (2015) found that auditors who consistently apply professional skepticism are more likely to identify irregularities that could compromise the integrity of financial statements. This supports the current findings in the Nigerian banking sector, demonstrating that increased skepticism positively affects the accuracy of audit reports. However, Gitonga (2012) argued that while professional skepticism is essential, it must be combined with other factors, such as independence and ethical standards, to achieve maximum audit effectiveness. While this is true, the present study suggests that even on its own, professional skepticism significantly enhances audit accuracy.

There is a significant effect of auditors' ethical standards on the accuracy of audit reports of some listed banks in Nigeria.

The finding that auditors' ethical standards have a significant and strong positive effect on the accuracy of audit reports is consistent with previous studies that highlight the critical role of ethical behavior in ensuring audit quality and integrity. For instance, Adeniyi (2017) emphasized that high ethical standards are fundamental to maintaining the credibility and reliability of financial reporting. The current study's result, with a coefficient of $B = 0.414$ and a highly significant t-value of 8.708, supports this claim, showing that adherence to ethical principles leads to more accurate audit outcomes in Nigerian banks. Similarly, Amadi and Renner (2021) found that ethical conduct among auditors reduces the risk of bias, fraud, and conflicts of interest, thereby enhancing the integrity of audit reports. This aligns with the current findings, which show that ethical standards have the strongest effect on audit accuracy among the tested variables. Ekpe and Mat (2015) also highlighted that ethical behavior strengthens public confidence in audit results and reinforces professional accountability. The significant effect observed in this study underscores their argument,

demonstrating that auditors' ethical standards directly contribute to the accuracy and reliability of financial reports. In addition, Odhiambo (2015) found that a strong ethical framework enhances auditors' ability to remain impartial and objective, particularly in high-pressure environments like the banking sector. This resonates with the current finding that ethical standards are the most influential factor in improving audit report accuracy in listed banks. However, Gitonga (2012) suggested that ethical standards must be complemented by independence and professional skepticism to maximize audit effectiveness. The present study confirms this to some extent but indicates that ethical standards alone have a more substantial impact than other factors in the context of Nigerian listed banks. In conclusion, the study aligns with existing literature, reinforcing the idea that maintaining high ethical standards among auditors significantly improves the accuracy of audit reports. This finding highlights the need for banks to promote ethical training and enforce strict professional codes to ensure audit integrity.

Conclusion

The findings from the regression analysis demonstrate that auditors' independence, professional skepticism, and ethical standards all have significant positive effects on the accuracy of audit reports in listed banks in Nigeria. Among these factors, ethical standards exert the strongest influence, followed by professional skepticism and auditors' independence. The rejection of all three null hypotheses confirms that each of these variables plays a crucial role in enhancing audit accuracy. These results highlight the importance of maintaining high ethical standards, fostering professional skepticism, and ensuring auditor independence to strengthen the reliability and credibility of audit reports in the Nigerian banking sector. The findings underscore the need for regulatory bodies and banking institutions to prioritize these factors to improve audit quality and promote financial transparency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, it is recommended that:

- i. Listed banks should strengthen policies that promote auditor independence to enhance the accuracy and reliability of audit reports.
- ii. Banks should provide continuous training to auditors to cultivate and reinforce professional skepticism, ensuring more thorough and objective audit evaluations.
- iii. Regulatory bodies and banks should enforce strict adherence to ethical guidelines and codes of conduct to uphold the integrity and accuracy of audit reports.

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